

AGRONOMIC CHARACTERIZATION AND EVALUATION OF FIELD PERFORMANCE OF VARIETIES OF SWEET POTATO IN FEDERAL CAPITAL TERRITORY (FCT), ABUJA

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ABSTRACT The study involved three field trials. First, a survey identified the sweet potato varieties cultivated in each of the six Area Councils of the FCT-Abuja. Subsequently, the field performance of selected varieties was evaluated in two trials conducted at the University of Abuja Teaching and Research Farm. Fresh biomass yield (t/ha), percentage of stand survival, number of storage roots/plots at harvest, number of marketable and unmarketable storage roots/plot, harvest index, root yield (t/ha), vine length (cm), number of vines per stand, number of leaves per stand, and tap root length (cm) were all recorded. The R- statistics software was used to do an analysis of variance (ANOVA) on the acquired data. The Least Significant Difference (LSD) was employed to differentiate treatment means that were significantly different ($p \leq 0.05$). In both cropping seasons, the results indicated that there was no significant difference ($p \leq 0.05$) in the varieties' length, number of leaves, leaf area, number of vines per stand, percentage of survival, total number of storage roots per plot, and number of unmarketable roots. The quantity of marketable roots, fresh biomass weight, and tuber length and weight of the chosen varieties, however, varied substantially ($p \leq 0.05$). Furthermore, significant variations in tuber weights were noted between the first and second trials. In the first trial, Ex-Igbarima exhibited the highest weight (5.00 kg), while Pofan dan Kano had the lowest weight (1.97 kg). In the second trial, King J had the highest weight (10.67 kg), and Pofan dan Kano had the lowest weight (5.63 kg). Based on the superior and efficient performance of King J, Ex-Igbarima, TIS-8164, and orange-fleshed varieties, farmers in the FCT are encouraged to cultivate these cultivars for commercial production.
Keywords: Sweet potato, Varieties, Characterization, Evaluation and Yield.

INTRODUCTION

The sweet potato (*Ipomoea batatas* (L) fertilization and moisture (Parwada *et al.*, Lam, is a member of the order Polemoniales 2011). Globally, sweet potatoes are and the family Convolvulaceae (Oggema *et* becoming more and more popular, and new *al.* 2007). After cassava and potatoes, it is markets are opening up for their use. the third most significant root and tuber crop However, their continuing sustainability worldwide (Laban *et al.*, 2015). With a short will necessitate alternative technologies growth cycle of three to five months, this that will enhance yield while lowering tuber crop offers smallholder farmers production costs, since the likelihood of a priceless flexibility in when to plant and global food crisis in sub-Saharan Africa harvest, whether they are in a zone with increases due to climate change (George *et* significant rainfall or one that is drier, prone *al.*, 2011; Stathers *et al.* 2015; van Ittersum, to drought, floods, or marginal soils, all 2016). Many small-holder farmers in while requiring few inputs (Amare *et al.*, Nigeria have adopted the labour-intensive 2014). According to Sanginga (2015), the and costly traditional traditions of planting crop can adjust to various agroecological sweet potatoes on mounds and occasionally settings and agronomic and cultural on flat land (Aina, 2002). approaches. It can grow anywhere from sea Adopting ridging is essentially a borrowed level to elevations of up to 2,500 meters, practice. Depending on their experiences with temperatures ranging from 15°C to and the region, farmers employ different 33°C. It is frequently grown without types of seedbeds to cultivate sweet fertilizer or irrigation (Parwada *et al.*, 2011) potatoes because tillage for seedbed and offers strong ground cover against weed preparation is generally time-consuming, costly, and labour-intensive. It can also invasion and erosion. In sub-Saharan Africa, sweet potatoes are crucial for increase soil erosion and, in certain enhancing impoverished households' situations, may not always boost yields. The health, livelihoods, and household and yield gap among smallholder farmers in national food security (Sanginga, 2015; Africa that keeps them from attaining Stathers *et al.* 2015). Particularly in tropical achievable yield gains from enhanced sweet countries where it is extensively grown, it potatoes may be mostly caused by tillage serves as a source of human food, animal practices and soil nutrient constraints, feed, and a bio-based industrial raw material according to Vugt and Franke (2018). for the production of plastics, sugar syrups, Ahmed *et al.*, (2012) discovered that the ethanol, butanol, flour, and confections best way to produce herbage for fodder (Lebot, 2009; Loebenstein and Thottappilly without sacrificing tuber output was to plant 2009; George *et al.*, 2011). In addition to sweet potatoes on ridges and harvest the being high in dietary fibre, minerals, vines 105 days after planting, or after the vitamins, and antioxidants such as phenolic plant had reached around 60% of its growth compounds (Lebot *et al.*, 2016), sweet phase. Chagonda *et al.*, (2014) observed that although plantings from mounds had shorter root lengths and poorer yields, those potatoes are also known to have anti-carcinogenic and heart disease-preventive qualities (Chsandrsekara and Kumar, from ridges had longer mean storage root lengths. Due to greater yield stability in marginal environments, sweet potatoes have become planting on the mound outperformed popular among farmers with limited planting on the ridges or the flat, with no resources. This is because they can produce discernible differences between the two. yields of up to 15 t/ha or more with minimal Regrettably, yields and annual yield growth

rates are dipping throughout Africa; in Development Abuja and the Potato Farmers Uganda, for instance, yields have dropped Association of Nigeria were all involved. by 1.9% (Antia, 2006). Average yields in The second and third experiments were field China and other developing Asian countries trials of certain varieties of sweet potatoes are 14 t/ha, while in Africa they are 5 t/ha during the 2023 and 2024 cropping seasons (Bovell-Benjamin, 2007). The country at the Teaching and Research Farm of Abuja produced an estimated 49,357 tons of sweet University, Faculty of Agriculture along potatoes in 2016. Its production is restricted Airport Road, which is characterized by a and fraught with difficulties, despite its hilly and rugged terrain (Balogun, 2001). nutritional and financial advantages. A long-The geology of the region is highlighted by bedrock complexes (Ujoh, *et al.*, 2010). potatoes in sub-Saharan Africa will be Following visits to the National Root Crops Research Institute (NRCI) outstation for increasing yield per area. In Abuja, Nigeria, sweet potato farming secondary data collecting and the Farmers needs to be prioritized to fight hunger and and Agricultural Development Project guarantee food security. In Africa, sweet offices (ADP) in the six Area Councils of potato yields currently range from 10.2 to 14 Abuja, the results were collected. Findings t/ha, which is lower than that of important were gathered and documented. A visit to crops like yams and cassava. This is mostly the Potato Farmers Association of Nigeria due to a lack of better diversity. For sweet (POFAN) and the Federal Ministry of potatoes to reach their full potential, farmers Agriculture was also conducted. Oral and the government must invest in better interviews and questionnaires were used to varieties and scientific research (Worku *et* gather data. Twenty potato farmers from *al.*, 2013). Despite its many benefits, this each local government area council were product is typically overlooked in questioned. Additionally, the farmers agricultural planning in the majority of particularly the more educated ones were tropical nations, including Nigeria. The given questionnaires. Additionally, NRCI study's goals are to fully document all of the staff members were interrogated, and sweet potato varieties in the Federal Capital pertinent records were acquired. Territory (FCT), give farmers in the FCT comprehensive information about the The field evaluation experimental site was potential of the varieties to help them cleared, packed and stumped using increase their productivity, assess each machetes, rakes and dibbers. Subsequently, variety's field performance in the FCT, the site will be ploughed, harrowed and identify the best variety for farmers in the pulverized into a fine tilth. Thereafter, the FCT to maximize yield, and ascertain which experimental layout was established using variety is most popular with FCT measuring tapes and pegs (60 cm high) consumers.

MATERIALS AND METHOD

Three experiments were carried out for the 87/0087 (TIS-8164)-White flesh sweet research. The first experiment focused on potato, (Mother Delight-(UMUSPO3), the characterization of all sweet potato Orange flesh sweet potato, UMUSP1 varieties in FCT in 2023. The National Root (NRSP/05/022)-King-J and Pofan Dan Crops Research Institute (NRCRI) Nyanya Kano (Local) variety. outstation in Nasarawa state, the Federal Ministry of Agriculture and Rural

ridges will be established with 6 ridges per plot. The experimental material used was six (6) varieties of sweet potatoes which were Buttermilk, Ex-Igbarima, TIS-

The experimental treatments whose effects per stand, tap root length (cm), fresh were evaluated include six varieties of biomass yield (t/ha), percentage of stand sweet potato which include; (A) Buttermilk, survival, number of storage roots/plots at (B) Ex-Igbarima, (C) TIS-87/0087-White harvest, number of marketable roots/plots, flesh sweet potato, (D) Orange flesh sweet number of unmarketable storage roots, potato ((Mother Delight-(UMUSPO3)), (E) harvest index, and root yield (t/ha) were (UMUSP1 (NRSP/05/022)-King-J and (F)- among the parameters that were measured. Pofan Dan Kano (Local) variety. All data collected were subjected to an Randomized Complete Block Design analysis of variance (ANOVA) using the R- (RCBD) with 3 replicates was used in the statistics package. Where the treatment study. Each replicate contains 6 plots, thus a means were significantly different ($p \leq$ total of 18 plots were used for the study. 0.05), the Least Significant Difference Each plot contained 4 ridges measured (LSD) was used to separate them. 3mx3m and was separated from the other

with the replicate by 0.5m pathway. Each **3. RESULTS**

replicate was separated from the other by a 1m access route for effective monitoring of

the experiment.

Stand establishment, vine length (cm), number of vines per stand, number of leaves

The prominent sweet potato varieties in FCT-Abuja are displayed in Table 1.

Table 1: Varieties of sweet potato varieties cultivated in FCT-Abuja.

Area Council	Varieties found
Abuja Municipal Area Council (AMAC)	UMUSP3 (CIP 440293) -MOTHER DELIGHT, TIS-87/0087(TIS-8164), UMUSP4 SOLO-GOLD, BUTTERMILK, UMUSP1 (NRSP/05/022)-KING-J, POFAN DAN KANO.
Abaji	UMUSP1 (NRSP/05/022)-KING-J, TIS-87/0087(TIS-8164), (NRSP/05/10D), BUTTERMILK, UMUSP3 (CIP 440293) -MOTHER DELIGHT, UMUSP4 SOLO-GOLD, POFAN DAN KANO.
Kwali	UMUSP2 (NRSP/05/10D), UMUSP2 (NRSP/05/022)-KING-J, BUTTERMILK, TIS-87/0087(TIS-8164), UMUSP3 (CIP 440293) - MOTHER DELIGHT, UMUSP4 SOLO-GOLD, POFAN DAN KANO.
Bwari	UMUSP3 (CIP 440293) -MOTHER DELIGHT, UMUSP4 SOLO-GOLD, TIS-87/0087(TIS-8164), BUTTERMILK, UMUSP1 (NRSP/05/022)-KING-J, CRI-OKUMKOM 35, POFAN DAN KANO. UMUSP1(NRSP/05/022)-KING-J,
Kuje	UMUSP2 (NRSP/05/10D), BUTTERMILK, UMUSP3 (CIP 440293) - MOTHER DELIGHT, UMUSP4 SOLO-GOLD, TIS-87/0087(TIS-8164), POFAN DAN KANO.
Gwagwalada	UMUSP3 (CIP 440293) -MOTHER DELIGHT, UMUSP4 SOLO-GOLD, BUTTERMILK, TIS-87/0087(TIS-8164), UMUSP1 (NRSP/05/022)-KING-J, POFAN DAN KANO.

Source: Fielddata collected in2023.

Tables 2 -8 respectively, illustrate how seasons. Additionally, there was no varietal differences affected the length of the discernible difference between the two vine, the number of leaves, the leaf area, the cropping seasons in the number of vines per percentage of survival, the number of vines stand at 4 and 12 WAP, respectively. per stand, the total number of storage roots per plot, and the number of unmarketable roots of potatoes in 2023 and 2024 cropping and the number of unmarketable roots of the seasons. Tables 2–5 show that there was no varieties in the 2023 and 2024 cropping seasons, respectively, did not differ significantly difference ($p \leq 0.05$) in the vine length, number of leaves, leaf area, and significantly ($p \leq 0.05$), as Tables 7 and 8 survival percentage at 4, 8, and 12 WAP, further demonstrate. respectively, between the two cropping

Table 2: Effect of Varietal Difference on the Vine Length of Potato

Treatment	Cropping seasons					
	1 st			2 nd		
	Weeks (WAP)	After	Planting	Weeks (WAP)	After	Planting
	4	8	12	4	8	12
Variety						
King J-UMUSPI	180.00	230.67	247.63	165.10	207.73	208.23
Ex-Igbarima	150.77	243.03	267.73	157.13	206.57	217.73
TIS-8164	172.47	200.50	230.97	133.43	193.93	216.63
Orange Flesh	154.77	164.67	202.23	157.27	165.67	204.03
Buttermilk	132.57	137.43	188.23	114.10	128.53	189.28
Pofan Dan Kano	120.50	132.53	178.37	120.93	140.77	214.50
Significance	NS	NS -	NS -	NS -	NS -	NS -
LSD (0.05%)	-					

Mean with the letter(s) are not statistically different at a 5% level of probability. * = Significant at a 5% level of probability. NS = Not significant at a 5% level of probability.

Table3: EffectofVarietalDifferenceontheNumberofLeaves

Treatment	Cropping seasons					
	1 st			2 nd		
	Weeks (WAP)	After	Planting	Weeks (WAP)	After	Planting
	4	8	12	4	8	12
Variety						
KingJ-UMUSPI	49.33	80.33	92.67	38.00	71.67	82.67
Ex-Igbarima	56.67	96.00	107.67	63.00	67.00	76.00
TIS-8164	36.33	70.00	108.00	53.33	61.00	78.33
OrangeFlesh	64.67	86.33	99.00	48.00	78.67	89.33
Buttermilk	51.33	57.33	73.00	38.33	81.67	81.33
PofanDanKano	35.00	62.00	74.67	42.00	64.33	80.00
Significance	NS -	NS -	NS -	NS -	NS -	NS -
LSD(0.05%)						

Mean with the letter(s) are not statistically different at a 5% level of probability. * = Significant at a 5% level of probability. NS = Not significant at a 5% level of probability.

Table 4: Effect of Varietal Difference on Leaf Area of Potato

Treatment	Cropping seasons					
	1 st			2 nd		
	Weeks After Planting (WAP)			Weeks After Planting (WAP)		
	4	8	12	4	8	12
Variety						
KingJ-UMUSPI	0.98	1.32	1.63	0.77	0.98	1.82
Ex-Igbarima	1.26	1.86	1.93	1.29	1.58	1.61
TIS-8164	1.38	1.76	1.77	1.24	1.58	1.72
OrangeFlesh	0.96	1.25	1.70	1.26	1.40	1.79
Buttermilk	1.06	1.42	1.68	0.61	1.50	1.41
PofanDanKano	0.52	0.84	1.22	0.90	1.30	1.50
Significance	NS	NS	NS	NS	NS	NS
LSD(0.05%)	-	-	-	-	-	-

Mean with the letter(s) are not statistically different at a 5% level of probability. * = Significant at a 5% level of probability. NS = Not significant at a 5% level of probability.

Table 5: Effect of Varietal Difference of Potato on Percentage of Survival

Treatments	Cropping seasons	
	Percentage of Survival	
	1 st	2 nd
Variety		
KingJ-UMUSPI	95.87	72.70
Ex-Igbarima	93.77	72.93
TIS-8164	93.77	85.43
OrangeFlesh	87.53	85.43
BUTTERMILK	85.43	72.93
PofanDanKano	83.33	79.33
Significance	NS -	NS -
LSD(0.05%)		

Mean with the letter(s) are not statistically different at a 5% level of probability. * = Significant at a 5% level of probability. NS = Not significant at a 5% level of probability.

Table 6: Effect of Varietal Difference on the Number of Vine of Potato per Stand.

Treatment	2023			2024		
	Weeks After Planting (WAP)			Weeks After Planting (WAP)		
	4	8	12	4	8	12
Variety						
King J-UMUSPI	2.00	4.00 ^{ab}	4.67	3.00	4.33 ^a	2.67
Ex-Igbarima	2.00	3.67 ^{ab}	4.33	2.67	2.67 ^c	4.00
TIS-8164	3.00	3.33 ^{ab}	4.67	3.00	3.00 ^{bc}	4.00
Orange Flesh	2.67	4.00 ^{ab}	5.00	2.67	4.00 ^{ab}	3.67
Butter Milk	3.00	4.33	5.33	2.67	3.67 ^{abc}	3.67
Pofan Dan Kano	2.00	^a	3.67	2.33	3.33 ^{abc}	3.67
Significance	NS	² .67	NS	NS	*	NS
LSD (0.05%)	-	¹ .36	-	-	1.03	-

Mean with the letter(s) are not statistically different at a 5% level of probability. * = Significant at a 5% level of probability. NS = Not significant at a 5% level of probability.

Table 7: Effect of Varietal Differences on the Total Number of Storage Roots

Treatments	Cropping seasons	
	Total Number of Roots	
	1 st	2 nd
Variety		
KingJ-UMUSPI	18.00	51.00
Ex-Igbarima	20.67	39.00
TIS-8164	14.67	37.33
OrangeFlesh	14.33	33.33
Buttermilk	18.00	39.33
PofanDanKano	14.67	47.00
Significance	NS -	NS -
LSD(0.05%)		

Mean with the letter(s) are not statistically different at a 5% level of probability. * = Significant at a 5% level of probability. NS = Not significant at a 5% level of probability.

Table 8: Effect of Varietal Differences on the Number of Unmarketable Roots of Potato

Treatments	Number of Unmarketable Roots	
	Cropping seasons	
	1 st	2 nd
Variety		
KingJ-UMUSPI	8.33	19.67
Ex-Igbarima	8.33	18.33
TIS-8164	6.33	19.67
OrangeFlesh	5.33	19.67
Buttermilk	8.33	13.00
PofanDanKano	4.67	18.33
Significance	NS	NS
LSD(0.05%)	-	-

Mean with the letter(s) are not statistically different at a 5% level of probability. * = Significant at a 5% level of probability. NS = Not significant at a 5% level of probability.

The number of marketable roots of the selected varieties of potato in the 2023 and 2024 cropping seasons is shown in Table 9. A significant difference ($p \leq 0.05$) was recorded in the number of marketable roots of the different varieties. In the 1st cropping season, the TIS - 8164 variety had the highest number (8.33) of marketable roots though not significantly different ($p \leq 0.05$) from all others except Pofan Dan Kano which had the least number_{nd} (3.67) of marketable roots. In the 2nd season, the King J-UMUSPI variety had the highest number (27.33) of marketable roots though not significantly different ($p \leq 0.05$) from all others except Buttermilk and Pofan Dan Kano.

Table 9: Effect of Varietal Differences on the Number of Marketable Roots of Potato.

Treatments	Number of Marketable Roots	
	Cropping seasons	
	1 st	2 nd
Variety		
King J-UMUSPI	7.33 ^{ab}	27.33 ^a
Ex-Igbarima	6.67 ^{ab}	20.67 ^{ab}
TIS-8164	8.33 ^a	21.00 ^b
Orange Flesh	7.00 ^{ab}	21.67 ^{ab}
Buttermilk	6.67 ^{ab}	19.33 ^b
Pofan DanKano	3.67 ^b	17.00 ^b
Significance	*	*
LSD (0.05%)	3.79	6.05

Mean with the letter(s) are not statistically different at a 5% level of probability. * = Significant at a 5% level of probability. NS = Not significant at a 5% level of probability.

The fresh biomass weight of selected varieties of potatoes as significantly influenced by variety in the 2023 and 2024 cropping seasons is shown in Table 10. The varietal differences had a significant effect ($p \leq 0.05$) on the fresh biomass weight of the potatoes.

The Ex-Igbarima (25.50 kg), TIS-8164 (22.90 kg) and Pofan Dan Kano (22.77 kg) had

the_{std}

highest fresh biomass in weight in the 1st cropping season. Similarly, in the 2nd cropping season, Ex-Igbarima (5.03) had the highest biomass weight though not significantly different ($p \leq 0.05$) from TIS-8164 (4.43 kg) and King J-UMUSPI (3.77 kg). The lowest biomass weight was recorded in Buttermilk (1.23 kg).

Table 10: Effect of Varietal Differences on the Fresh Biomass Weight of Potato.

Treatments	Cropping seasons	
	1 st	2 nd
Variety		
King J-UMUSPI	17.70 ^b	3.77 ^{ab}
Ex-Igbarima	25.50 ^a	5.03 ^a
TIS-8164	22.90 ^a	4.43 ^a
Orange Flesh	18.77 ^b	1.83 ^{bc}
Buttermilk	18.17 ^b	1.23 ^c
Pofan DanKano	22.77 ^a	1.50 ^c
Significance	*	*
LSD (0.05%)	4.65	2.23

Mean with the letter(s) are not statistically different at a 5% level of probability. * = Significant at a 5% level of probability. NS = Not significant at a 5% level of probability.

The length of tubers of potatoes as influenced by the varietal difference in the 2023 and 2024 cropping seasons is shown in Table 11. A significant difference ($p \leq 0.05$) was recorded in the length of tubers in the 1st season. The King J-UMUSPI variety had the longest tubers (17.10 cm) and was not significantly different ($p \leq 0.05$) from all others except the Buttermilk and Pofan Dan Kano. However, in the 2nd cropping season, no significant difference ($p \leq 0.05$) was recorded in the tuber length.

Table 11: Effect of Varietal Differences on Length of Tubers of Potato

Treatments	Cropping seasons	
	Length of Tubers	
	1 st	2 nd
Variety		
King J-UMUSPI	17.10 ^a	18.17
Ex-Igbarima	12.93 ^{abc}	14.57
TIS-8164	15.80 ^{ab}	14.93
Orange Flesh	14.30 ^{abc}	13.70
BUTTERMILK	12.80 ^{bc}	12.80
Pofan Dan Kano	10.83 ^c	12.20
Significance	*	NS -
LSD(0.05%)	4.19	

Mean with the letter(s) are not statistically different at a 5% level of probability. * = Significant at a 5% level of probability. NS = Not significant at a 5% level of probability.

The weight of tubers of potatoes as significantly influenced by the varietal difference in the 2023 and 2024 cropping seasons is shown in Table 12. In both cropping seasons, a significant difference ($p \leq 0.05$) was recorded in the weight of tubers among the varieties. The Ex-Igbarima (5.00 kg) had the highest tuber weight though not significantly different ($p \leq 0.05$) from King the J-UMUSPI, and Buttermilk variety. The lowest tuber weight of 1.97 kg was recorded in Pofan Dan Kano. In 2nd season however, the King J-UMUSPI variety had the heaviest tuber weight of 10.67 kg though not significantly different ($p \leq 0.05$) from all others except the Buttermilk and the Pofan Dan Kano variety.

Table 12: Effects of Varietal Differences on the Weight of Tubers of Potato

Treatments	Cropping season	
	Weight of Tubers	
	1 st	2 nd
Variety		
King J-UMUSPI	4.13 ^a	10.67 ^a
Ex-Igbarima	5.00 ^a	7.37 ^{ab}
TIS-8164	2.40 ^b	9.40 ^{ab}
Orange Flesh	2.67 ^b	6.67 ^{ab}
Buttermilk	4.33 ^a	6.20 ^b
Pofan Dan Kano	1.97 ^b	5.63 ^b
Significance	* 1.45	*
LSD(0.05%)		4.40

Mean with the letter(s) are not statistically different at a 5% level of probability. * = Significant at a 5% level of probability. NS = Not significant at a 5% level of probability.

4. DISCUSSION

high yield, disease resistance, and marketable qualities (Aniedu, and Oti, Mother Delight (UMUSPO3) is renowned because it is high in vitamins (especially beta-carotene-derived vitamin A), minerals, and carbohydrates. The TIS-87/0087 sweet potato variety is high in minerals, vitamins (especially A (UMUSPO3) demonstrates good resistance to pests, Cylas weevil, and drought and can be grown in a variety of environments and agricultural zones (Ndolo, *et al.*, 2001). Its shelf life can be further extended with the right storage methods, increasing its marketability and cutting down on waste. The variety has strong resistance to potato virus disease (SPVD), and pests like Rees, (2001). Its resistance to drought guarantees steady culinary offerings. It can be used to make many different kinds of food, both conventional and contemporary. Its flavour and consistency make it ideal for frying, baking, boiling, and other methods (Woolfe, 1992). This type and consistency make it ideal for frying, baking, boiling, and other methods (Woolfe, 1992). Because it gives farmers a steady source of income, this variety has a major positive economic impact on the area. It is a crop that is economically viable due to its (Rees *et al.*, 2001). By giving farmers a

steady source of income, the TIS-87/0087 known for its high yield potential, rich in variety considerably boosts the local and essential nutrients, including vitamins A and regional economies. It is a crop that is C, fibre, and minerals such as potassium and economically viable due to its high yield, magnesium. With high beta-carotene disease resistance, and marketable qualities content (Ukom, *et al.*, 2009). The variety (Aniedu and Oti 2012).

The UMUSP1 (NRSP/05/022), also known as King-J, is known for its high yield such as sweet potato virus disease (SPVD) potential. It produces a significant number and sweet potato weevils. Pofan Dan Kano of large, marketable tubers, making it a sweet potato is well adapted to the climatic preferred choice for farmers. It is rich in and soil conditions of the Kano region. It essential nutrients, including high levels of can thrive in the semi-arid environment carbohydrates, vitamins (notably vitamin A typical of northern Nigeria, making it a from beta-carotene), and minerals. This reliable crop for local farmers. Adeniji & nutritional profile makes it an excellent food Aloyce (2013). This variety is known for its source for combating vitamin A deficiency nutritional content, including and malnutrition (Low, & Van Jaarsveld, carbohydrates, dietary fibre, vitamins, and 2008). This variety exhibits good resistance minerals. And is particularly valued for its to common sweet potato diseases and pests, high beta-carotene content, contributing to such as sweet potato virus disease (SPVD) improved vitamin A intake among and sweet potato weevil as well as drought. consumers.

King-J is adaptable to a range of climatic On the Field performance of the varieties of potato in Abuja. The results indicate that conditions, including both humid and semi- arid regions. This makes it a versatile crop vegetative growth parameters such as vine suitable for different environments, length, leaf count, leaf area, number of vines enhancing food security in diverse per stand, percentage survival, and number agricultural zones. According to (Ndolo *et al.* of stands per plot at harvest did not show significant variation, except for the number *al.*, 2001; Tumwegamire *et al.*, 2001), King- J sweet potatoes have a relatively good of stands per plot at harvest, where King J exhibited the highest count (91.96%) and Pofan Dan Kano showed the lowest reducing post-harvest losses.

Buttermilk sweet potato is noted for its high (70.87%) in the first trial, although no yield potential, rich in essential nutrients, significant differences were noted in the including carbohydrates, vitamins (notably second trial. This outcome is attributed to vitamin A from beta-carotene), and the genetic control of the growth minerals. It is resistant to common diseases characteristics of these sweet potato and pests, such as sweet potato virus disease varieties. An example of this can be seen in (SPVD) and sweet potato weevil. And is an experiment by (Abonusum *et al.*, 2021) adaptable to a range of climatic conditions, on the growth and yield characteristics of including both humid and semi-arid regions five different sweet potato varieties grown (Ndolo *et al.*, 2001). BUTTERMILK sweet in the guinea savanna ecological zone of potato has demonstrated good drought Ghana, which indicated no differences in tolerance and has a relatively good storage vegetative growth.

life, which helps in reducing post-harvest Concerning their yield and yield losses. It can be used in a variety of dishes, components such as the number of including traditional recipes and modern marketable roots, number of unmarketable roots, fresh biomass weight, length of preparations.

The Ex-Igbarima sweet potato variety is tubers, and weight of tubers, no significant

difference was found in the total number of roots across both cropping seasons; however, there was a significant difference in the number of marketable roots, with TIS-8167 Delight, TIS-8164 (TIS-8163), and UMUSP4 Solo-Gold, BUTTERMILK, and Pofan dan Kano the lowest (3.79) in the first cropping season. In the second cropping season, King J recorded the highest number and characterized in the 6-area council of (27.33), while Pofan dan Kano had the lowest yield (17.00). TIS-8167's higher number and yield component but not in growth of marketable roots is due to its greater measurements. The first trial's highest yield resistance to the pest known as Cylas. There was found in Ex-Igbarima. In the second were no differences in the number of trial, King J. produced the best yield, while unmarketable roots, but variations were Pofan Dan Kano produced the lowest yield noted in the fresh biomass weight; during over both cropping seasons. the first trial, Ex-Igbarima had the highest weight (25.50 kg) and King J had the lowest Farmers in the Federal Capital Territory are

(17.70 kg), while in the second trial, Ex-Igbarima showed the highest weight (5.03 kg), whereas Buttermilk had the lowest weight (1.23 kg). A significant difference in cultivars' tuber length was observed in the first trial, where King J had the highest length (17.10 cm) and Pofan dan Kano had the lowest (10.83 cm), while in the second trial, no significant differences were recorded. Additionally, significant differences in tuber weight were evident during both trials; in the first trial, Ex-Igbarima had the highest weight (5.00 kg) and Pofan dan Kano the lowest (1.97), while in the second trial, King J had the highest weight (10.67 kg) and Pofan dan Kano the lowest (5.63). The same findings were reported by (Abonuusum *et al.*, 2021).

CONCLUSION AND

RECOMMENDATION

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